

Phytochemical screening and GC-MS analysis of different crude extracts of *Gloriosa superba* (L).

^{1*}R.Balamurugan, ² P.V. Sivakumar, ³Debasish dikshit ⁴ P.Thamizhiniyan

¹Research scholar, Department of Botany, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar, Tamilnadu

²Assistant Professor, Department of Botany , Thiru Kolanjiappar Govt Arts & Science college Virudhachalam. (Deputed) from annamalai university, Tamilnadu

³Research scholar, Department of Botany, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar, Tamilnadu

⁴The professor and Head, Department of Botany, Annamalai University, Tamilnadu

*Corresponding Author : R.Balamurugan

ABSTRACT

Gloriosa superba (L). also known as Malabar glory lilly, is a commercially important medicinal plant that has diverse medicinal applications, and eventually due to over exploitation this plant is facing local extinction. According to one of the ancient proverbs in India, there is no plant has been used by man since ancient times as medicine for curing various ailments. In recent times, there is has been upsurge of interest in focus on the importance of medicinal plants and traditional health systems in solving the health care problems of the world. The present study aim on the phytochemical screening of gloriosa superba different crude extract and showed that presence of different phytochemicals for ethanol, methanol, and acetone extracts. In ethanol extract Alkaloid Flavonoid, Glycoside, Saponins, Steroids, Phenols, Tannins, and Terpenoids; was found where in methanol extract Alkaloid Flavonoid, Glycoside, Saponins, Steroids, Phenols, Tannins, and Terpenoids; and acetone extract found in Alkaloid Flavonoid, Glycoside, Saponins, Steroids, Phenols, and Terpenoids. But methanol shows highest phytochemical were present. In analysis of different crude extract also carried out GC-MS where in ethanol extract 22 compounds present with highest RT value of 18.576 the methanolic extract 27 compounds present with highest RT value of 19.123 and acetone extract 17 compounds present with highest RT value of 19.325. the higher phytocompounds, an important of *Gloriosa superba* (L), was found in S1, S2, and S3 accessions in good concentration.

Key words: *Gloriosa superba* (L), phytochemical screening, GC –MS, Methanol

INTRODUCTION

Gloriosa superba Linn, is an important medicinal plant belonging to the family Liliaceae [1,2]. It is a semi-woody herbaceous branched climber reaching approximately 5 meters in height, with brilliant wavy-edged yellow and red flowers [3,4]. Which is one of the endangered species among the medicinal plants [5,6]. It is extensively scattered in the tropical and sub-tropical parts of India. It is adapted to different soil textures and climatic variations. The plant grows in sandy-loam soil in a mixed deciduous forest in sunny positions [7,8]. Being native to India, especially Southern India it is known as the glory lily or climbing lily in English [9]. In some Districts, farmers cultivate the plant species for its seeds. Tuber is a rich source of alkaloid colchicines [10]. This plant has gained importance in medicine in recent years for the production of colchicines on a large scale [11]. The tubers are commonly used for the treatment of inflammation, ulcers, bleeding piles, white discharge, scrofula, skin diseases, leprosy, indigestion, helminthes, snake bites, intermittent fever, baldness, and debility [12,13] Most of the research findings are plant oriented products aimed at identifying chemical compounds, especially secondary metabolites [14]. They are like alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, tannins, glycosides, saponins, steroids, phenolic compounds. It has been a well - known plant the Indian Ayurveda and pharmacological industries as well. It is mainly due to the presence of alkaloids like colchicine (C₂₂ H₂₅ O₆ N) and its derivatives like gloriosin and colchicocide (C₂₇ H₃₃ O₁₁ N), along with benzon acid, salicylic acid, Steroids and resinous substances, and therefore, the demand for this plant is increasing day by day [15]. Other compounds such as cornigerine, lumicolchicine, 3-demethyl-N-formyl-N-deacetyl-lumicolchicine, 3-demethyl-g-lumicolchicine, 3-demethyl colchicines, colchicocide, tannins, and superbine have been isolated from plants. The seeds contain a novel colchicine glycoside, 3-o-dimethylcolchicine-3-o-a-D-glucopyranoside. The tubers contain B-sitosterol, lumicolchicines, and 2-hydroxy-6-methoxy benzoic acid. Moreover, it has been reported that researchers have isolated luterlin from the roots, N-formyl-deacetyl colchicines from the flowers of *Gloriosa superba* [16,17,18]

The tuberous root stock of glory lily, boiled with Sesame oil, is applied twice a day to the joints, affected by arthritis, reducing pain [19]. Seeds are used for relieving rheumatic pain and as a muscle relaxant [20,21]. The tuber, which is useful for itching, skin diseases including wounds and ailments caused by vitiated kapha and vata, can be administered to a delivered mother along with a spirituous drink to relieve her postnatal complaints [22]. It is pungent, thermogenic, and used as a purgative [23]. In the world market, the tubers are considered rich sources of colchicine and gloriosine [24,25] Roots are acrid, anthelmintic, antipyretic, bitter, digestive, expectorant, highly poisonous, and promote expulsion of the placenta [26]. Most of the medicinal plants were the best source for a variety of new herbal products. In the current scenario, WHO estimates that 80% of people from all over the world are interested in traditional medicine. Medicinal plants are commonly known as people's friends providing food, fuel, and medicine [27]. Various kinds of pharmaceutical compounds from plants were used as alternative sources for the development of medicines. When compared to other systems of medicine, Ayurveda uses more plant based

medicines for the treatment of ailments. Because of the modern life style, numerous new diseases have been identified lately. The remedies for all diseases could be present in nature, but most of the potentially valuable treasures in medicinal plants as bioactive compounds are unexplored and underutilized. A healthy new generation could be formed due to the systematic use of these valuable medicinal compounds and plants [28,29].

Medicinal plants resences are major sources of Indian traditional and modern medicine Medicinal plants have been a rich source of biologically active compounds and play an important role in drug discovery [30]. Different parts, such as the leaf, root, stem, fruit, seed, and park, are used to obtain several phytochemical constituents. Medicinal plants are rich in flavonoids, and every group of flavonoids has the capacity to act as antioxidants [31]. Among them, flavones and catech components act as the most powerful flavonoids for protecting the body against ROS [32,33].

The other flavonoid components, such as quercetin, kaempferol, myricetin, and rutin, have antioxidant, antiinflammatory, antiviral, and antiallergic activities as well as anticancer activities [34,35]. Among Indian ayurvedic herbs, a number of thirty have shown antitumor activities [36]. Although certain pharmacological studies have been carried out on this plant, to the best of our knowledge, there is a report on phytochemical and GC-MS analysis of *G. superba* tubers. In this present work, we have reported the preliminary phytochemical and GC-MS studies on the traditional medicinal plant *G. superba* tubers [37].

MATERIALS METHODS

Preparation of plant extract

Fresh tubers were collected and, washed thoroughly under running tap water, washed with sterile distilled water, and cut in to the tuber's in slender shapes under the shade. They were grind in to coarse powder by using a mechanical pulverizer. About 100g of powder were repeatedly extracted with ethanol, methanol, acetone, n- hexane, and ethyl acetate, in a 500 ml round bottom flask with 250 ml of solvent. The reflux time for each solvent was 20 cycles for complete extraction for using the Soxhlet apparatus. The extract was filtered and finally dried at room temperature. the filtrate was collected and concentrated by using a rotary evaporator (Heidolph) under controlled conditions of temperature and pressure.

Phytochemical Screening

Chemical tests for the screening and identification of bioactive chemical constituents like alkaloids, carbohydrates, glycosides, saponins, phenolic compounds, phytosterols, proteins, amino acids, flavonoids, and tannins, in the medicinal plants under study were carried out in extracts using standard procedures.

1. Screening for Alkaloids

Crude extract was mixed with 2 ml of 1% HCL and heated gently. Mayer and Wagner reagents were then added to the mixture, and the turbidity of the resulting precipitate was taken as evidence for the presence of alkaloids.

2. Screening for Flavonoids

Crude extract was mixed with a few fragments of magnesium ribbon, and concentrated HCL was added drop – wise. A pink scarlet color appeared after a few minutes, which indicated the presence of flavonoid.

3. Screening for Glycosides

Crude extract was mixed with 2 ml of chloroform, then 2 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added carefully and shaken gently. A reddish brown color indicated the presence of a steroidal ring, i.e. glycone protein of the glycoside.

4. Screening for Saponins

Crude extract was mixed with 5 ml of distilled water in a test tube, and it was shaken vigorously. The formation of stable forms was taken as an indication of the presence of saponins.

5. Test for Steroids

Crude extract was mixed with 2 ml of chloroform, and concentrated H₂SO₄ was added sideways. A red color was produced in the lower chloroform layer, as indicated. The presence of steroids another test was performed by mixing crude extract with 2 ml of chloroform and then 2 ml of each of concentrated H₂SO₄ and acetic acid were poured into the mixture. The development of greenish coloration was indicated. The presence of steroids.

6. Screening for phenols

Crude extract was mixed with 2 ml of a 2% solution of FeCl₃ a blue - green or black coloration indicated the presence of phenols.

7. Screening for Tannins

Crude extract was mixed with 2 ml of a 2% solution of FeCl₃ a blue - green or black coloration indicated the presence of tannins.

8. Screening for Terpenoids

Crude extract was dissolved in 2 ml of chloroform and evaporated to dryness. To this, 2 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added and heated for about 2 minutes. a grayish color indicated the presence of terpenoids.

Table 1: preliminary phytochemical tests for the presence of active constituents in *Gloriosa superb* tuber extract

S.NO	Solvent's extract/ name of the Compound's	Ethanol	Methanol	Acetone	n-Hexane	Ethyl acetate
1.	Alkaloid	+++	++	++	+	+
2.	Flavonoid	+	++	+	-	-
3.	Glycoside	+++	++	+	+	+++
4.	Saponins	+	++	+	-	-
5.	Steroids	+	+++	++	-	-
6.	Phenols	+++	++	++	+	+
7.	Tannins	+++	++	-	-	+++
8.	Terpenoids	+	++	+	-	+

(+ = Slight; ++ = Normal; +++ = High; - = Negative)

GC-MS ANALYSIS

GC-MS analysis of the ethanol, methanol, and acetone extracts of *Gloriosa superb L.* was carried out at the Velore Institute of Technology (VIT). A Velore. GC Clarus 500 Perkin Elmer system comprising a AOC-20i auto sampler and gas chromatography interfaced to a pass petometer (GC-MS) instrument was used, applying the following conditions: Elite-1 silica capillary column (30mm x0.25mm ID x M μ Mdf composed of 100% Dimethyl poly siloxane), operating in electron impact mode at 70 ev was used. Helium (99.99%) is generally used as a carrier gas with a constant flow of 1ml/min an injection volume of 0.5 μ l (split ratio of 10: 1) an injector temperature 250⁰C. And the ion source temperature 280⁰C. The oven temperature is generally programmed from 110⁰C, with an increase of 10⁰C/min, to 200⁰C, then 5⁰C/ min up to 280⁰C, finally ending with a 9 min isothermal at 280⁰C. Mass spectra were taken at 70ev with a scan interval of 0.5 seconds and fragments from 45to450 Da. GC total running time is 36 minutes. The plant extract was dissolved in methanol and filtered with polymeric solid phase extraction (SPF). Column and analyzed for different components. The spectra of the components were compared with the database of spectra of known components stored in the GC-MS library. Measurement of peak areas and data processing were carried out by Turbo-Mass OCPTVS-Demo SPL software.

Figure 1: GC-MS chromatogram of tuber ethanol extract of *Gloriosa superba .L*

Table 2: (Fig – 1) Phyto-components obtained through GC–MS analysis isolated from Ethanolic tuber extracts of *Gloriosa superba* L.

S.NO	RT	Compound name	M.W.	Formula	Peak area%
1	7.881	Benzenemethanol	124	C7H8O2	1.59
2	8.316	4-hydroxy-Salicylalcohol	124	C7H8O2	2.16
3	9.307	Benzenemethanol	124	C7H8O2	3.27
4	9.862	4-hydroxy-1,2-benzenediol	124	C7H8O2	2.32
5	9.917	3-methyl-Benzenemethanol	124	C7H8O2	4.58
6	12.858	3-hydroxy-Salicylalcohol	124	C7H8O2	5.62
7	13.188	Salicylalcohol	124	C7H8O2	1.98
8	17.025	1,2-benzenediol	124	C7H8O2	2.71
9	17.280	4-methyl-Benzenemethanol	124	C7H8O2	18.94
10	18.110	3-hydroxy-Nicotinicacid	263	C16H25O2N	4.98
11	18.936	Decylester Benzenemethanol	124	C7H8O2	18.57
12	19.071	4-hydroxy-2,4,6-cycloheptatrien-1-one	106	C7H6O	4.50
13	19.901	1,3-benzenediol	124	C7H8O2	1.45
14	25.668	2-methyl-4h-1,3-benzodioxin	212	C14H12O2	3.47
15	26.814	2-phenyl-Benzenemethanol	124	C7H8O2	2.72
16	27.024	3-hydroxy-1,2-benzenediol	124	C7H8O2	5.83
17	27.544	4-methyl-7-chloro-1,3,4,10-tetrahydro-10-hydroxy-1-imino-3-[3-trifluoromethyl]	406	C20H14O2N2ClF3	4.86

Figure 2: GC-MS chromatogram of tuber Methanol extract of *Gloriosa superba* .L

Table 3: (Fig – 2) Phyto-components obtained through GC–MS analysis isolated from Methanolic tuber extracts of *Gloriosa superba* L.

S.NO	RT	Compound name	M.W.	Formula	Peak area %
1	2.819	Hydrazine	128	C7H16N2	1.76
2	3.434	1-(5-hexenyl)-1-methyl-Thiodiglycolicanhydride	132	C4H4O3S	3.97
3	3.604	Topotecan Hydrazine	421	C23H23O5N3	9.32
4	7.841	1,1-dimethyl- Hydrazine	60	C2H8N2	19.12
5	8.516	1,1-dimethyl- Mercaptamine	60	C2H8N2	5.69
6	8.626	Dimethyl-cyano-phosphine Acetamide	77	C2H7NS	2.56
7	8.666	n-methyl-2-(methylamino)-2-thioxo Thiazole	87	C3H6NP	1.26
8	8.806	4,5-dihydro-2-methyl- Carbamicacid	132	C4H8ON2S	9.76
9	9.027	1-methylethylester Propanamide	101	C4H7NS	1.67
10	9.437	2-hydroxy-n-methyl- Silane	103	C4H9O2N	3.92
11	9.892	dimethyl- Aceticacid	103	C4H9O2N	2.78
12	10.012	methoxy- Aceticacid	60	C2H8Si	7.36
13	10.387	methoxy- Diglycolicacid	90	C3H6O3	1.15
14	13.098	N-methoxy-1-ribofuranosyl-4-imidazole carboxylic amide	90	C3H6O3	6.22
15	17.095	Acetamide	134	C4H6O5	4.02
16	18.695	2,2'-thiobis-(ethylamine)	273	C10H15O6N3	5.34
17	18.895	N-morpholinomethyl-isopropyl-sulfide	148	C4H8O2N2S	1.61

Figure 3: GC-MS chromatogram of tuber Acetone extract of *Gloriosa superba* L

Table 4: (Fig – 3) Phyto-components obtained through GC–MS analysis isolated from Acetone tuber extracts of *Gloriosa superba* L.

S.NO	RT	Compound name	M.W.	Formula	Peak area %
1	3.214	OCTADECANOIC ACID	284	C18H36O2	8.19
2	3.279	OCTADECANOIC ACID	284	C18H36O2	2.85
3	3.404	OCTADECANOIC ACID	284	C18H36O2	3.62
4	3.489	EICOSANOIC ACID	312	C20H40O2	5.08
5	9.422	OCTADECANOIC ACID	284	C18H36O2	1.55
6	13.028	EICOSANOIC ACID	312	C20H40O2	1.20
7	17.190	N-HEXADECANOIC ACID	256	C16H32O2	15.04
8	18.080	DOCOSANOIC ACID	340	C22H44O2	2.80
9	18.805	TETRACOSANOIC ACID	368	C24H48O2	19.32
10	18.976	HEPTADECANOIC ACID	270	C17H34O2	3.68
11	25.668	NONADECANOIC ACID	298	C19H38O2	4.98
12	25.738	N-HEXADECANOIC ACID	256	C16H32O2	1.40
13	26.258	OCTADECANOIC ACID, 2-(2-HYDROXYETHOXY)ETHYL ESTER	372	C22H44O2	1.16
14	26.789	PENTADECANOIC ACID	242	C15H30O2	2.17
15	26.994	PENTADECANOIC ACID	242	C15H30O2	8.07
16	27.494	PENTADECANOIC ACID, 14-BROMO	320	C15H29O2Br	3.22
17	27.824	OCTADECANOIC ACID, 2-HYDROXY-1,3-PROPANEDIYL ESTER	624	C39H76O5	2.00

Fig-5 Screening Test for Flavonoids

Fig-6 Screening test for Glycosides

Fig-7 Screening Test for Saponins

Fig- 8 Screening Test for Steroids

Fig- 9 Screening Test for Phenols

Fig- 9 Screening Test for Terpenoids

Fig- 10 Screening Test for Tannins

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The bioactive chemicals examined in the tuber extract of *G. superba* revealed the presence, absence, and not detection of compounds as listed Ethanol, methanol, acetone, and extracts of *Gloriosa superba* tubers contain alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, steroids, tannins, and terpenoids, with an exception emphasis on phenols. According to the stated statement that the ethanol, methanol, acetone, and extract of *G. superba* contains at least all the phytochemicals except phenolic compounds. GC-MS analysis of drugs revealed the presence of various phytochemicals, including alkaloids and other observed structured compounds in, GC-MS analysis in our findings. The GC-MS analysis is a valuable method that has been increasingly applied to the analysis of medicinal plants for nonpolar components, volatile essential oils, fatty acids, and alkaloids. The *Gloriosa superba* L of the Ariyalur region (S1,S2,S3,) subjected to GC-MS analysis, retrieved 57 major phytocomponents. Such as gamma - sitosterol, stigmast - 7- en-3ol, cholest-5-ene, 3- ethoxy, 3- beta stigmast - 8 (14) - en - 3, beta-ol ergost- 8- en -3 ol, 14-methyl-, (3 beta, 5 alpha), benzene methanol , -4 hydroxy, salicyl alcohol, 1,2- benzenediol, 3-methyl, benzene methanol, -3 hydroxy, 1,2- benzenediol, 4- methyl benzenemethanol, 3- hydroxyl nicotinic acid, decyl ester, 2,4,6 - cycloheptatrien, 1,3 benzenediol, 2- methyl 4H - 1,3- benzodioxin, 2 - phenyl benzenemethanol.

Medicinal plant derived phytochemicals are an important source of medicinal plants for eco friendly applications [39]. Plants have an almost limitless ability to synthesize aromatic substances, most of which are phenols or their oxygen-substituted derivatives. Most are secondary metabolites, of which at least 12,000 have been isolated, a number estimated to be less than 10% of the total [40]. In the present study, the methanol extracts of all the samples showed the maximum yield of phytochemicals. However, the methanol extract of *G. superba* showed good results for phytochemicals like phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, and tannins [41].

The interest in medicinal plant exploration as a source of pharmacologically active compounds has increased worldwide [42]. In most developing countries around the world, plants are the main medicinal sources used in treating infectious diseases. The various phytochemical compounds detected are known to exhibit medicinal activity as well as physiological activity [43]. There are records that show the benefits of these compounds detected in *G. superba*. For example: Many of the previous reports show that the isolated pure compounds with biological activity were alkaloids. Naturally occurring alkaloids are nitrogenous compounds that constitute the basic active principles of flowering plants. Alkaloids are formed as metabolic products and have been reported to be pharmaceutically active [44]. Some of the simplest bioactive phytochemicals consist of a single substituted phenolic ring. Phenolics are the largest group and have been said to account for most of the antioxidant activity of plant extracts. Phenolics and alkaloids detected in the extracts are compounds that have been documented to possess medicinal properties and health-promoting effects [45,46].

Plant steroids are known to be important for their cardiogenic activities; they possess insecticidal and anti-microbial properties. They are routinely used in medicine because of their profound biological activities. Glycosides are nonvolatile and, lack fragrance, and serve as defense mechanisms against predation by many microorganisms, insects, and herbivores [47]. Plant saponins help humans fight fungal infections, combat microbes and viruses, boost the effectiveness of certain vaccines, and knock out some kinds of tumor cells, particularly lung and blood cancers. These compounds served as natural antibiotics, which help the body fight infections and microbial invasion [48]. Tannins have been traditionally used for the protection of inflamed surfaces of the mouth and the treatment of catarrh, wounds, hemorrhoids, and diarrhea. Plant tannins have been recognized for their pharmacological properties and are known to make trees and shrubs. Flavonoids are widely distributed group of polyphenolic compounds, characterized by a common benzopyrene ring structure. The biological functions of flavonoids apart from their antioxidant properties, include protection against allergies, inflammation, free radicals, platelet aggregation, microbes, ulcers, hepatotoxins, viruses, and tumors. Flavonoids reduce cancer by interfering with the enzymes that produce estrogen [49,50].

CONCLUSION

Medicinal plants are natural sources of bioactive compounds to treat life threatening diseases. *G. superba*, is an important medicinal plant, used as an antidote for snake poison, is in demand commercially. The tuber is poisonous, when consumed in high quantities. This plant is also considered a colchicine source for the chemical constituents of the medicine industry. Additionally, it would be useful to produce a high amount of colchicine for pest control based on natural products. Several studies have reported that *G. superba* is rich in various biologically active compounds, which could serve as a potential source of crude drugs that can be used as a complementary source of traditional medicines.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors sincerely acknowledge the valuable support provided by Annamalai university chidambaram and ,Vellore institute of Technology vellore; and Indian institute of Technology Chennai.

REFERENCES

1. S.V. Ahire a comparative phytochemical composition of *Gloriosa superba*.L callus tissue and it's natural leaf and fresh tuber roots extracts Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research. 2020 march; 3 (7): 2349-5162.
2. Hemant badwaik, Tapan kumar giri, D.K. Tripathi, Mukesh singh and Abdul hanif kahn, a review on pharmacological profile for phytomedicine known as *Gloriosa superba*.L research journal of pharmacognosy and phytochemistry. 2011; 3 (3): 0975-4385.

3. Kaliyaperumal, Ashokkumar, *Gloriosa superb* (L.): A brief review of its phytochemical properties and pharmacology. International journal of pharmacognosy and phytochemical research 2015; 7 (6); 1190 – 1193.
4. Sachin chaudhary, Abdel – Nasser EL – shorbagi, Bhawna shridhar, Mandeep kumar gupta, Harish Chandra verma A review on phytochemical and pharmacological profile of *Gloriosa superba* linn. International research journal of pharmacy. 2019; 10 (4) 2230-8407.
5. Maroyi A, van der maesen LJG. *Gloriosa superb* L. (family colchicaceae): remedy or poison journal of medicinal plants research 2011; 5 (26): 6112 – 6121.
6. Mariappan senthilkumar phytochemical screening of *Gloriosa superba* L. – from different geographical positions. International journal of science and research publications. January 2013; 3 (1) 2250.3153.
7. H. K. Badola, Endangered medicinal plant species in Himachal Pradesh. A report on the International Workshop on “Endangered Medicinal Plant Species in Himachal Pradesh”, organized by G.B. Pant Institute of Himalayan Environment and Development at Himachal Unit, Mohal-Kullu during 18-19 March 2002. Curr. Sci 2002; 83: 797-798.
8. G. Sivakumar, K.V. Krishnamurthy, *Gloriosa superba* L. - a very useful medicinal plant. In: Recent Progress In Medicinal Plants, USA, 2002, pp. 465-82.
9. S. E. Trease, D. Evans, *Colchicum seed and corn*. In: Pharmacognosy, 12th edn. Balliere Tindall, London, 1983, pp. 593-597.
10. Srivastava UG, Chandra V. *Gloriosa superba* Linn. (Kalihari) - An important colchicines producing plant. J Res Indian Med. 1977; 10:92-5.
11. C.K. Kokate, A.P. Purohit, S.B. Gokhale, Pharmacognosy, Nirali Prakashan, Pune, 2004, pp. 506.
12. Baskar UC, Dash D, Mahapatra AK, Estimation of Colchicine in tubers of *Gloriosa superba* L, originated from different agroclimatic zones of Odisha, India, International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research. 2012; 4(3):157-161.
13. Gupta LM, Raina RC, Raina R, Gupta M. Colchicine content in *Gloriosa superba* L – J. Res. SKUAST-J. 2005; 4(2):238-241.
14. Rizwan SA, Abdul rahman AG, Raisuddin A, Wajhu Q, and Suliman A. Analysis of inorganic and organic constituents of myrrh resin by GC-MS and ICP-MS: An emphasis on medicinal assets. Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal. 2017; 25:788-794.
15. Megala,S, Elango, bioactive compounds analysis tuber and seed of *Gloriosa superb* GC-MS method. International journal of recent scientific research. October 2012; 3 (10), PP.871-873
16. Badwaik H, Giri TK, Tripathi DK, Singh M, Khan AH. A review on pharmacological profile for Phytomedicine known as *Gloriosa superba* Linn. Research Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytomedicine 2011; 3(3): 103-107.

17. Suri OP, Gupta BD, Suri KA. A new glycoside, 3-odemethylcolchicine-3-o-alpha-d-glucopyranoside from *Gloriosa* seeds. *Natural Product Letters* 2001; 15(4):217- 219.
18. Clewer HWW, Green SS, Tutin F. The constituents of *Gloriosa superba*. *Journal of Chemical Society* 1915; 107: 835-846.
19. Kaliyaperumal, Ashokkumar, *Gloriosa superb* (L.): A brief review of its phytochemical properties and pharmacology. *International journal of pharmacognosy and phytochemical research*.2015; 7 (6): 1190 – 1193.
20. Singh, V.K. selected Indian folk medicinal claims and their relevance in primary health care programme glimpses plant res., 1993, 10: 147 - 152
21. Dharmendra Singh, Manish mishra, Anirudha singh yadav. Evaluation of phytocontents of extract of *Gloriosa superb* Linn. By thin layer chromatography and their antioxidant activity. *American journal of pharmtech research*.2012; 2 (4): 2249 – 3387.
22. Singh, V.K. selected Indian folk medicinal claims and their relevance in primary health care programme. *Glimposes plant res.*, 1993,10: 147 – 152.
23. Aradhana mishra, Neeta singh phytochemical analysis of leaves and tubers of *Gloriosa superb* L. Endangered plant. *International journal of advanced research and development*. July 2019; 4(4) 2455 – 4030
24. Nadkarni AK. *Indian Materia Medica*. Popular Prakashan limited, 2002, 579-581.
25. Srivastava UC, Chandra V. *Gloriosa superba* Linn. (Kalihari) - An important colchicine producing plant. *J. Res. Indian Med.* 1977; 10:92-95.
26. Prajapati ND, Purohit SS, Sharma AK, Kumar T. *A hand book of Medicinal Plants: Agro bios publishers (India); Jodhpur, 2003, 221-234.*
27. Asha V, Narmratu S, Aravind K. Phyto chemical investigation and thin layer chromatography of *Asparagus racemosus* (Family – Asparagaceae) methanolic leaves extract. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Pharmaceutical and Bioscience*. 2013; 3(1):15-18.
28. Nikhila GS, Sangeetha G, Preetha TS, and Swapna TS GC –MS analysis of phytochemical compounds present in the rhizome of *Gloriosa superb* L. *Journal of pharmacognosy and phytochemistry*. 2016 ;5(5) : 2278 – 4136.
29. Elizabeth T, Aneesh TP, Della GT, Anandhan R. GC –MS analysis of phytochemical compounds present in the rhizomes of *nervilia aragoana*. *Asian J pharm and clin Res*. 2013; 6(3): 68 -74.
30. Saradha devi, K. M., Annapoorani, S. and Ashokkumar, K. Hepatic antioxidative potential of ethyl acetate fraction of *Cynodon dactylon* in Balb/c mice. *J. Med. Plant. Res.*, 2011, 5(6): 992-996.
31. Ashokkumar, K., Kumarakurubaran, S. and Saradha Devi, K.M. Reverse phase-high performance liquid chromatography-diode array detector (RP-HPLCAD) analysis of flavonoids profile from curry leaf (*Murraya koenigii*. L). *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*. 2013. 7(47): 3393-3399.

32. Saradha devi, M., K. Ashokkumar and S. Annapoorani Identification and determination of flavonoids, carotenoids and chlorophyll concentration in *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) by HPLC analysis. *Natural Products Research*, 2015. 29 (8): 785-790.
33. De Groot H. Reactive oxygen species in tissue injury. *Hepatogastroenterology*. 1994, 41:328–332.
34. Fraga CG, Mactino US, Ferraro GE, Coussio JF, Boveris A. Flavonoids as antioxidants evaluated by in vitro and in situ liver chemiluminescence. *Biochem Pharmacol.*, 1987, 36:717–720.
35. Hillwell B. Free radicals, antioxidants and human disease: curiosity, cause or constipation? *Lancet*, 1994, 344:721–724.
36. Adhvaryu, M.R., Reddy, N. and Parabia, M.N. Antitumor activity of four ayurvedic herbs in Dalton Lymphoma Ascites bearing mice and their short-term in vivo cytotoxicity on DLA cell line. *Afr. J. Tradit. Complement Altern Med.*, 2010, 5(4): 409-418.
37. T.Anantha kumar, M. Jayachandran, P. Shanmuga velan, V. Veeraputhiran phytochemical and GC –MS studies on therapeutically active *Gloriosa superba* Flowers. *Journal of natural products and resources*. October 2015;1 (1): 2455 - 0299.
38. Kumaravel S, Praveenkumar P, and Vasuki, P. GC-MS study on microbial degradation of Lindane. *International Journal of Applied Chemistry*. 2010; 6(3):363-366.
39. Venkatachalam MR, Jebasan A. Larvicidal activity of *Hydrocotyl javanica* Thump extract against *Culex quinquefasciatus*. *J. Exp to Zool. India*. 2010; 4:99-101.
40. Schultes RE. The kingdom of plants. In WAR. Thomson (ed.), *Medicines from the Earth*. McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, N.Y. 1978, 208.
41. Devi NN, Femina W. GC-MS analysis of *Gloriosa superba* medicinal plant of Tamilnadu. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*. 2012; 5(1):343-345.
42. Rios JL, Recio MC. Medicinal plants and antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2005; 100:80-84.
43. Sofowora A. *Medicinal Plants and Traditional Medicines in Africa*. Chichester John Wiley & Sons New York. 1993; 97-145.
44. Doughari JH. Antimicrobial activity of *Tamarindus indica* Linn. *Tropical Journal of Pharmacy Research*. 2006; 5:597.
45. Liu RH. Potential synergy of phytochemicals in cancer prevention: mechanism of action. *Journal of Nutrition*. 2004; 134:3479-3485.
46. Cowan MM. *Plant Products as Antimicrobial Agents*. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*. 1999, 564-582.
47. De M, Krishina De A, Banerjee AB. Antimicrobial screening of some Indian spices. *Phototherapy Research*. 1999; 13:616-618.
48. Sodipo OA, Akiniyi J, Ogunbanosu. Studies on certain characteristics of extracts of bark of *Pansinystalia macruceras* (K.Schem) Piere. Exbeile. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Science*. 6, 83-87.

49. Ogunleye DS, Ibitoye SF. Studies of antimicrobial activity and chemical constituents of *Ximenia americana*. *Tropical Journal of Pharmacy Research*. 2003; 2(2):239- 241.
50. Naik GH, Priyadharsini Kl, Hari mohan. Free radical scavenging reaction and phytochemical analysis of triphala. An ayurvedic formulation. *Current science*. 2006; 90(8): 1100 - 1105